

Deliverable 3.6

GUIDANCE ON STATISTICAL LEARNING METHODOLOGIES ON FEDERATED/DIFFERENTIALLY PRIVATE DATASETS FOR CLINICAL USE CASES

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive review of federated learning (FL) tools, emphasizing their application within the PHEMS project. The document outlines theoretical principles of FL, technical frameworks for implementation, and covers key aspects such as data governance, local model training, and global model aggregation. In addition to widely recognized FL frameworks, this deliverable also explores the relevance of Swarm Learning (SL) and OMOP-tailored FL frameworks. The frameworks considered in this deliverable must demonstrate long-term viability not only through technical performance but also through governance, licensing, and sector-specific adoption, ensuring that any implementation within PHEMS not only supports advanced analytics but also adheres to the highest standards of data protection and privacy.

List of abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
DP	Differential Privacy
FedAvg	Federated Averaging
FedMA	Federated Matched Averaging
FedMD	Federated Model Distillation
FedMeta	Federated Meta-Learning with Fast Convergence and Efficient Communication
FedML	Federated Machine Learning
FedProx	Federated Proximal
FedSGD	Federated Stochastic Gradient Descent
FL	Federated Learning
FLARE	Federated Learning with Adjusted learning rate
FTL	Federated Transfer Learning
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HFL	Horizontal Federated Learning
IID	Independent and Identically Distributed
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
PICU	Pediatric Intensive Care Unit
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
TEEs	Trusted Execution Environments
TFF	TensorFlow Federated
VFL	Vertical Federated Learning

1. Fundamentals of Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) is a machine learning (ML) paradigm that allows multiple organizations to collaboratively train a shared model using their local datasets, without the need to transfer data to a central location. This approach is fundamentally different from traditional centralized learning, where data from various sources is collected in a single repository for training. Federated learning operates in a decentralized manner, where each participating institution downloads a global model, trains it locally on its private data, and then only the model updates (e.g., gradients or model weights) are shared. An aggregation algorithm is finally applied to aggregate the updates from all participating institutions to improve the global model iteratively.

The detailed architecture of the federated infrastructure implemented in PHEMS, including the functions of the central server/node and technical configurations, is described in [Deliverable 2.1](#): This current document will focus on the core principles of federated learning that can guide the clinical use cases, which will perform specific analytics and machine learning tasks using the PHEMS federated architecture.

1.1. Machine Learning basics

To understand federated machine learning, it is essential to first grasp the fundamentals of traditional machine learning. ML is a branch of artificial intelligence that focuses on creating systems that can learn from data. It uses algorithms and statistical models to identify patterns within data, allowing computers to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed. The learning process improves over time as the model is exposed to more data, refining its accuracy and generalization. This typically involves two main phases:

1. **Training phase:** During this phase, input data vectors are fed into a machine learning model to enable it to learn a function that maps these inputs to output class labels or values. The learning process involves updating the model's parameters incrementally to minimize the difference between the predicted outputs and the actual target values. This learning can be categorized into several types: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning and reinforcement learning (overview in Section 1.2).
2. **Prediction phase:** In this phase, the trained model is used to predict the output or class label for new input data vectors. The accuracy of these predictions determines the effectiveness of the machine learning model.

1.1.1. Formal Definition of Machine Learning¹

In general mathematical terms, machine learning can be defined as the process of optimizing a function or model to map input data $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ to target outputs $Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_2)$.

A learning algorithm searches for a function f such that:

$$f: X \rightarrow Y$$

The goal is to minimize a loss function $Loss(f(X), Y)$, which measures the error between predicted outputs $f(X)$ and the true outputs Y . This optimization is typically done via techniques discussed in Section 1.3, where the model iteratively adjusts its parameters to reduce the error. This definition has evolved significantly over time as new methods and algorithms are developed. Initially, linear models and basic neural networks dominated the field, but the landscape has rapidly expanded to include more complex architectures like deep neural networks, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), as discussed below. Each of these models introduces new ways to define the mapping function and optimize the learning parameters.

In addition to advancements in model architectures, there have been numerous innovations in optimization techniques, loss functions, and training methods in order to improve model performance and generalization. Furthermore, the introduction of advanced methods such as transfer learning, reinforcement learning, and federated learning represents significant iterations in how machine learning models are defined, trained, and deployed².

1.2. Types of ML techniques

Machine Learning algorithms are generally classified into four main types: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning, as illustrated in Figure 1. Below, we provide a brief overview of each approach. Detailed explanations and formal description of these methods, further reading of ³ is recommended.

¹ Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (n.d.). Springer Series in Statistics The Elements of Statistical Learning Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction.

² Rahman, A., Debnath, T., Kundu, D., Khan, M. S. I., Aishi, A. A., Sazzad, S., Sayduzzaman, M., & Band, S. S. (2024). Machine learning and deep learning-based approach in smart healthcare: Recent advances, applications, challenges and opportunities. In *AIMS Public Health* (Vol. 11, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.3934/publichealth.2024004>

³ Sarker, I. H. (2021). Machine Learning: Algorithms, Real-World Applications and Research Directions. In *SN Computer Science* (Vol. 2, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-021-00592-x>

Figure 1: Classification of machine learning algorithms².

1.2.1. Supervised Learning

Supervised learning involves training a model on labeled data, meaning that the input data has corresponding correct outputs. Supervised learning tasks include classification (discrete labels) and regression (continuous labels):

- **Classification techniques:**
 - **Naive Bayes:** A probabilistic classifier based on Bayes' theorem with the assumption of independence among predictors. It is computationally efficient and works well for high-dimensional data, but its performance can degrade if the independence assumption is violated.
 - **Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA):** A linear classifier that reduces dimensionality by projecting data into a lower-dimensional space while preserving class separability. LDA assumes Gaussian distribution of each class and is effective in scenarios with multiple classes.
 - **Logistic Regression:** A statistical model used for binary and multiclass classification that predicts probabilities using the logistic function. Regularization techniques such as L1 (LASSO) and L2 (Ridge) are often used to improve generalization and prevent overfitting.
 - **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** SVMs find a hyperplane that separates data into classes with the maximum margin. SVM is effective in high-dimensional spaces and supports kernel methods, allowing for nonlinear classification.
 - **K-nearest neighbors (KNN):** A non-parametric and instance-based learning algorithm that assigns class labels based on the majority class of the nearest

neighbors. While simple and effective for small datasets, it can be computationally expensive for large datasets.

- **Decision Trees:** A flowchart-like tree structure where each internal node represents a feature, each branch represents a decision rule, and each leaf node represents the outcome. Decision trees are easy to interpret but prone to overfitting.
- **Random Forest:** An ensemble method that combines multiple decision trees to improve accuracy and control overfitting. Random forests use bagging and feature randomness to create multiple decision trees and aggregate their results.
- **Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) and XGBoost:** Gradient boosting sequentially builds trees where each tree corrects the errors of its predecessors. XGBoost improves on standard GBM by implementing regularization and handling missing data efficiently.
- **Regression techniques:**
 - **Linear Regression:** Predicts a continuous output based on a linear relationship between the input variables and the output. Multiple linear regression involves multiple input variables.
 - **Polynomial Regression:** Extends linear regression by fitting a polynomial equation to the input data, capturing non-linear relationships between input and output variables.

1.2.2. Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning deals with data without labeled outcomes. The goal is to find hidden patterns or intrinsic structures in the data:

- **Clustering techniques:**
 - **K-means Clustering:** Partitions the data into k clusters by minimizing the distance between data points and their respective cluster centroids. It is sensitive to the initial cluster centers and can be affected by outliers.
 - **DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise):** A density-based clustering algorithm that can identify arbitrarily shaped clusters and is robust to noise and outliers. It does not require the number of clusters to be predefined.

- **Hierarchical Clustering:** Builds a tree-like structure of clusters using either a bottom-up (agglomerative) or top-down (divisive) approach. This method is useful when there is no prior knowledge of the number of clusters.
- **Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM):** A probabilistic model that assumes that the data is generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions. GMMs provide a soft clustering of data, where each point is assigned a probability of belonging to a particular cluster.
- **Dimensionality reduction techniques:**
 - **Principal Component Analysis (PCA):** Transforms the original high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional space by identifying the directions (principal components) that capture the most variance in the data. PCA is often used to reduce data complexity while retaining important information.
 - **Feature Extraction and Selection:** Methods like **variance thresholding**, **Pearson correlation**, and **ANOVA** are used to select the most important features. Feature selection reduces model complexity, enhances interpretability, and prevents overfitting.

1.2.3. Semi-Supervised Learning

Semi-supervised learning combines both labeled and unlabeled data. This approach is particularly useful when labeled data is scarce but unlabeled data is abundant. By using a small amount of labeled data to guide the learning process, semi-supervised algorithms can make better use of the unlabeled data, improving accuracy compared to using only labeled data.

1.2.4. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) focuses on training an agent to take actions in an environment to maximize cumulative rewards. The agent learns through trial and error, receiving feedback from its environment after each action.

- **Q-learning:** A model-free reinforcement learning algorithm that learns the quality of actions, telling the agent which action to take under specific conditions.
- **Deep Q Networks (DQN):** Combines Q-learning with deep learning techniques, using neural networks to approximate the action-value function. It is particularly useful in environments with large state and action spaces.

1.2.5. Deep Learning

Deep learning, a subset of machine learning, focuses on using neural networks with many layers (deep neural networks) to automatically learn representations from large datasets. It is particularly effective for tasks involving unstructured data, such as images, videos, and text.

- **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):** CNNs are specialized for processing grid-like data such as images. They use convolutional layers to automatically extract spatial features from the input.
- **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs):** RNNs are designed for sequential data, such as time series or natural language, by maintaining a hidden state that captures information from previous inputs.
- **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)** networks are a type of RNN that addresses the vanishing gradient problem, making them suitable for long-term dependencies.
- **Autoencoders:** Unsupervised neural networks that learn to compress and reconstruct input data. Autoencoders are often used for dimensionality reduction and feature extraction.

1.3. Optimization algorithms⁴.

Optimization is the process of minimizing or maximizing the Loss function to find the best model parameters or hyper-parameters. In ML, there are two types of parameters: model parameters (such as weights in neural networks) that are learned from the data and hyper-parameters, which define the architecture or learning process (such as learning rate, number of neighbors in KNN, etc.). The key focus in ML optimization is on hyper-parameter optimization (HPO), as tuning these hyper-parameters significantly impacts model performance. HPO aims to automate this tuning process by employing various optimization algorithms, which are especially crucial for complex models like deep neural networks or tree-based algorithms that have a large number of hyper-parameters.

Several optimization techniques are available to achieve these goals, ranging from traditional methods such as:

- **Gradient descent**, which is suited for continuous hyper-parameter tuning, to more advanced techniques.

⁴ Yang, L., & Shami, A. (2020). On hyperparameter optimization of machine learning algorithms: Theory and practice. *Neurocomputing*, 415, 295–316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUCOM.2020.07.061>

- **Grid search and random search** are widely used methods that explore the search space either exhaustively (grid search) or randomly (random search), but they can be inefficient for complex models or large datasets due to their lack of focus on regions that are likely to yield optimal results.
- **Bayesian optimization** offer improvements by using past evaluation results to guide the search process toward promising areas of the search space, reducing the number of evaluations needed to find the optimal hyper-parameters.
- **Metaheuristic algorithms** such as **Genetic Algorithms (GA)** and **Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)** simulate natural processes to find optimal or near-optimal solutions in large or complex search spaces. These methods are particularly effective for complex models with large numbers of hyper-parameters, such as deep neural networks or ensemble methods (e.g., random forests and gradient-boosting machines). GA evolves a population of potential solutions over several generations, while PSO involves particles that "swarm" the search space, continuously updating based on their own and the group's best-known positions.

The choice of optimization technique depends on the nature of the machine learning problem, the hyper-parameter space, and computational resources. While grid search and random search may suffice for simpler problems or smaller datasets, more complex tasks benefit from advanced methods such as Bayesian optimization or metaheuristic algorithms, which can explore larger search spaces more efficiently and often lead to better-performing models.

1.4. Distributed machine learning

With the growth of data and complexity of models, traditional centralized ML approaches have become impractical for very large datasets. Distributed Machine Learning (DML) addresses this by splitting the training process across multiple compute nodes, which can operate in parallel. DML introduces concepts such as data parallelism and model parallelism⁵:

- **Data parallelism:** Here, the dataset is divided into smaller, non-overlapping subsets, and each subset is processed independently across multiple computing nodes. The

⁵ Berloco, F., Bevilacqua, V., & Colucci, S. (2024). Distributed Analytics For Big Data: A Survey. *Neurocomputing*, 574, 127258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUCOM.2024.127258>

main idea is that different nodes (or workers) execute the same machine learning model but on different portions of the dataset simultaneously.

- **Model parallelism:** a single machine learning model is split into different parts, and each part is assigned to a different computing node. Instead of distributing the data, model parallelism distributes the computation by splitting the model itself across multiple nodes.

1.5. Formal definition of Federated Learning⁶

Similar to centralized ML, Federated learning can be mathematically formalized as an optimization problem. Consider a global objective function that aims to minimize the aggregate loss across all participating clients. The function is represented as:

$$\arg \min_{w_L} \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Loss}(X_p, Y_p, w_L)$$

Where:

- P denotes the number of participating clients.
- X_p, Y_p represent the input and output data for the p -th client, respectively.
- w_L is the set of model parameters being optimized.
- $\text{Loss}(X_p, Y_p, w_L)$ is the loss function for the p -th client, which measures the discrepancy between the predicted outputs and actual outputs for that client's local data.

The goal is to find the set of parameters w_L that minimizes the total loss across all clients, thereby creating a model that generalizes well to the data from all participating entities.

1.6. Federated Learning architectures, network topology⁷

Federated learning can be implemented using different architectural models, primarily:

- **Client-server architecture:** This is the most common implementation of federated learning, where a central server acts as a coordinating node. The server distributes the initial global model to all clients, collects the updated model parameters after local

⁶ Zhang, C., Xie, Y., Bai, H., Yu, B., Li, W., & Gao, Y. (2021). A survey on federated learning. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 216, 106775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.KNOSYS.2021.106775>

⁷ Rodríguez-Barroso, N., Stipcich, G., Jiménez-López, D., Ruiz-Millán, J. A., Martínez-Cámara, E., González-Seco, G., Luzón, M. V., Veganzones, M. Á., & Herrera, F. (2020). *Federated Learning and Differential Privacy: Software tools analysis, the Sherpa.ai FL framework and methodological guidelines for preserving data privacy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2020.07.009>

training, and aggregates these updates to refine the global model. This process is repeated until the model converges. The client-server model simplifies coordination and management but requires trust in the central server's security and integrity.

Figure 2: Client-server FL architecture, similar to the PHEMS architecture, processing layer.

- Peer-to-peer architecture:** In this decentralized architecture, there is no central coordinating server. Instead, each client communicates directly with other clients to exchange model updates. This approach enhances data privacy by eliminating a single point of control but increases computational complexity and communication overhead. The peer-to-peer model is less common but is useful in scenarios where enhanced security and privacy are required.

Figure 3: Peer-to-peer FL architecture.

1.7. A note on Swarm Learning (SL) architectures

Swarm Learning is a decentralized machine learning architecture that combines edge computing, blockchain-based networking, and peer-to-peer coordination to maintain data confidentiality without a central coordinator (Figure). Its architecture allows participants, called Swarm edge nodes, to perform local training on their data while sharing model parameters via the Swarm network. Using blockchain ensures secure and transparent participation, while model parameters are merged across nodes without raw data exchange. This decentralized approach, implemented through the Swarm Learning Library (SLL), provides robustness in privacy and fault tolerance beyond traditional federated learning systems.

Figure 4: Overview of SL architecture, adapted from⁸

1.8. Federated Learning paradigms in terms of data samples

Federated learning (FL) can be categorized into three primary types: Horizontal Federated Learning (HFL), Vertical Federated Learning (VFL), and Federated Transfer Learning (FTL). These categories are defined based on the degree of overlap in data features and samples across the datasets of participating clients. Each category is suited for different practical problems, depending on the nature of the data held by each participant.

- **Horizontal federated learning (HFL):** Horizontal Federated Learning, also known as sample-based federated learning, is used when the datasets of each client have more common features than common samples. In this scenario, the data across

⁸ Wamat-Herresthal, S., Schultze, H., Shastry, K. L., Manamohan, S., Mukherjee, S., Garg, V., Sarveswara, R., Händler, K., Pickkers, P., Aziz, N. A., Ktena, S., Tran, F., Bitzer, M., Ossowski, S., Casadei, N., Herr, C., Petersheim, D., Behrends, U., Kern, F., ... Schultze, J. L. (2021). Swarm Learning for decentralized and confidential clinical machine learning. *Nature*, 594(7862). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03583-3>

clients have the same feature space but different samples. HFL is guided by the feature dimension of the data and is effective when multiple participants have datasets with similar types of information (features) but different individuals (samples). In HFL, the training process involves taking data segments that share the same features but come from different samples and combining them for joint training. This effectively enlarges the sample space by uniting data samples from various participants. As a result, the model trained under HFL benefits from a broader dataset, enhancing its accuracy and generalization ability. This approach is commonly used in situations where different institutions or devices collect similar types of data, such as in collaborative healthcare studies where multiple hospitals share anonymized patient data with similar attributes but different patients. This is the case in the PHEMS network.

- **Vertical federated learning (VFL):** Vertical Federated Learning is employed when the datasets of each client share more samples than features. This means that different clients have datasets containing information about the same set of samples but with different features. VFL is particularly useful in scenarios where different organizations possess complementary data about the same individuals. In VFL, the data is aligned based on common samples. The training process involves first aligning the datasets to identify overlapping samples, then jointly training on the combined features of these samples. This type of federated learning allows participants to collaborate by using diverse datasets that capture different aspects of the same user base, thereby building a more comprehensive model. For example, in a financial scenario, one company might have user demographic data while another has transaction history data; VFL can combine these to create a robust credit scoring model without exchanging sensitive user data.
- **Federated transfer learning (FTL):** Federated Transfer Learning is designed to handle cases where both the feature space and the sample space differ significantly across participants (e.g., between two hospitals). The core idea is to leverage shared samples or representations that exist between the two organizations. Here's how FTL overcomes the challenge of different features⁹:
 - **Shared Representation Learning:** Even though Hospital A and Hospital B have different features, FTL learns a shared representation by mapping each party's feature space into a common latent space. This means that while the

⁹ Saha, S., & Ahmad, T. (2021). Federated transfer learning: Concept and applications. *Intelligenza Artificiale*, 15(1), 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.3233/IA-200075>

raw features (e.g., demographics vs. treatments) are different, the model learns to represent them in a form that is compatible for joint learning. Techniques such as neural networks are commonly used to extract high-level representations that capture the most relevant information from both feature spaces. These learned representations are then transferred between parties without sharing the original data.

- **Collaborative Updates via Model Sharing:** In FTL, each hospital trains a local model on its own dataset. They then share model parameters or gradients. These updates are aggregated in a way that ensures the overall model benefits from the knowledge of both hospitals. The hospitals iteratively improve their local models using insights from each other, even though they have different features. The common knowledge (e.g., patterns in outcomes or disease progression) emerges from combining updates from both hospitals.

1.9. Phases of Federated Learning¹⁰

Overall, FL operates under two phases:

- **Model training phase:** In this phase, the training of a ML model is carried out collaboratively across multiple decentralized sites (clients). This process can vary according to the network architecture, but typically follows these steps:
 - Initialization: A central coordinating server initializes a global model, which is then distributed to all participating clients (e.g., each hospital). This model could be untrained or pre-trained based on prior knowledge or data.
 - Local training: Each client trains the global model locally using its private dataset. This involves feeding the input data vectors into the model and adjusting the model's parameters based on a loss function that measures the gap between the predicted outputs and the actual labels or values.
 - Model update: In network architectures with a central server, instead of sending raw data back to the central server, each client sends only the updates to the model parameters (e.g., gradients) that have been computed during local training. These updates represent the local learning without exposing any actual data. In peer-to-peer architectures, the model parameters are exchanged and merged

¹⁰ Hu, K., Gong, S., Zhang, Q., Seng, C., Xia, M., & Jiang, S. (2024). An overview of implementing security and privacy in federated learning. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 57(8). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-024-10846-8>

across nodes through a blockchain-based system. This peer-to-peer interaction ensures that learning occurs directly between participants while preserving data privacy and confidentiality¹¹.

- Aggregation: The central server receives the parameter updates from all clients and aggregates them. This aggregation step is crucial for creating a global model that reflects the collective knowledge and data diversity of all participating entities.
 - Iteration: Steps 2 through 4 are repeated iteratively, with each round of training refining the global model further. The process continues until a stopping criterion, such as model convergence or a maximum number of iterations, is reached.
- **Model inference phase:** Once the global model is fully trained, it can be deployed for inference. In this phase, the model is used to make predictions on new data. Each client can use the shared model to make local predictions without needing to share new data with the central server or other clients. This decentralized inference approach maintains data privacy while allowing all participants to benefit from the collaboratively trained model.

Figure 1: Overview of a federated learning framework with a central server.

¹¹ Warnat-Herresthal, S., Schultze, H., Shastry, K. L., Manamohan, S., Mukherjee, S., Garg, V., Sarveswara, R., Händler, K., Pickkers, P., Aziz, N. A., Ktena, S., Tran, F., Bitzer, M., Ossowski, S., Casadei, N., Herr, C., Petersheim, D., Behrends, U., Kern, F., ... Schultze, J. L. (2021). Swarm Learning for decentralized and confidential clinical machine learning. *Nature*, 594(7862). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03583-3>

1.10. Type of model distribution: exchanging models, parameters and gradients¹²

In FL, models, parameters, or gradients can be exchanged between a central server and local clients. The term "exchanging models" is commonly used, but in practice it can refer to:

- **Exchanging models:** Full models are shared between the server and clients, but this approach is costly and can present security risks.
- **Exchanging model parameters:** This method typically applies to neural networks, where the parameters (or weights) are exchanged between clients and servers. It reduces communication costs but assumes that all clients share the same model architecture, which can be limiting if data structures vary across clients.
- **Hybrid approaches:** These combine different methods, such as exchanging initial parameters and then receiving updated models, depending on the specific requirements of the application or environment.

Type	Concept	Advantages	Disadvantages
Exchanging Models	Models are sent between server and clients	Ease of implementation	High communication cost; Less secure
Exchanging Gradients	Only gradients are exchanged between entities	Lower communication cost; Higher security	Local models divergence
Exchanging Model Parameters	Only weight and parameters are exchanged	Lower communication cost; Higher security	Needs unified client model architecture;
Hybrid Approach	Merging two or more of the above approaches	Fit for specific cases	Generated frameworks may not be re-used

Table 1: Model exchange methods in FL.

2. FL aggregation algorithms¹³

Model aggregation is the process of combining the updates (such as models, parameters, or gradients) sent by individual clients into a single global model. Aggregation methods can

¹² Moshawrab, M., Adda, M., Bouzouane, A., Ibrahim, H., & Raad, A. (2023). Reviewing Federated Learning Aggregation Algorithms; Strategies, Contributions, Limitations and Future Perspectives. In *Electronics (Switzerland)* (Vol. 12, Issue 10). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12102287>

¹³ Qi, P., Chiaro, D., Guzzo, A., Ianni, M., Fortino, G., & Piccialli, F. (2024). Model aggregation techniques in federated learning: A comprehensive survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 150, 272–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURE.2023.09.008>

vary, including averaging model weights, computing weighted sums based on the size or quality of the data, and even hierarchically combining updates across multiple servers before final aggregation. This process ensures that the global model progressively improves with each iteration of distributed learning across clients. Various aggregation techniques have been developed, with some already integrated into open source frameworks (discussed later in Section 2). In this section, known aggregation algorithms are discussed.

2.1. Average aggregation

In the average aggregation method, the server combines the updates from all participating clients by computing their average. Whether these updates are model parameters, weights, or gradients, the aggregation follows this formula: the total sum of all client updates is divided by the number of clients. If "N" is the number of clients and w_i represents the updates from each client, the global update W is calculated as:

$$W = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^N w_i$$

2.2. Clipped average aggregation

This method extends the basic average aggregation by clipping model updates to a predefined range before averaging. This step prevents outliers or malicious updates from skewing the global model. If w_i represents the model updates from clients and $clip(x, c)$ is a function that limits values between $[-c, c]$, the clipped aggregate update is calculated as:

$$W = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^N clip(w_i, c)$$

2.3. Secure aggregation

This method focuses on enhancing privacy during aggregation using techniques like homomorphic encryption or secure multiparty computation. It ensures that client data remains confidential by enabling encrypted or privacy-preserving computations, making it suitable for highly secure environments.

2.4. Differential privacy average aggregation

In this approach, random noise is added to each client's model updates to ensure privacy. These noisy updates are aggregated by the server, which balances privacy protection with

model accuracy. The aggregate update is calculated by adding noise vectors n_i to the client updates:

$$W = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^N (w_i + b.n_i)$$

2.5. Momentum aggregation

This method helps speed up convergence in federated learning by appending a "momentum" term, which captures the direction of model updates over time, to the client's updates. The server collects these momentum-enhanced updates to generate a final global model.

2.6. Weighted aggregation

In this method, each client's update is given a different weight depending on factors as data quality or client performance. The aggregate update is calculated as:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (a_i \cdot w_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N a_i}$$

2.7. Bayesian aggregation

This approach uses Bayesian inference to aggregate model updates, incorporating uncertainty in model parameters. This helps improve the generalizability of the model and reduce overfitting.

2.8. Adversarial aggregation

To defend against malicious clients, this method uses techniques like outlier detection or secure enclaves to identify and mitigate fraudulent updates before they can negatively impact the global model.

2.9. Quantization aggregation

Model updates are compressed by reducing their bit size before being sent to the server for aggregation. This improves communication efficiency by reducing the amount of data transmitted.

2.10. Hierarchical Aggregation

This approach aggregates updates at different levels of a hierarchy, such as local servers, before sending them to the central server. This reduces communication overhead and makes it scalable for large systems.

2.11. Personalized aggregation

In this method, the global model is tailored for each client based on its unique data characteristics during the aggregation process, while maintaining privacy.

2.12. Ensemble-based aggregation

Models are trained on different subsets of clients, and the resulting models are combined to produce a final model. This method helps handle non-IID data, and it can be combined with weighted aggregation for improved accuracy.

2.13. Comparison of FL aggregation methods¹⁴

Approach	Main Concept	Advantages	Disadvantages
Average Aggregation	Average the clients updates	Simple and easy to implement	Sensitive to outliers and malicious clients
		Can improve model accuracy	May not perform well in cases of non-IID data
Clipped Average Aggregation	Clip the model updates to a predefined range before taking the average	Reduces the effect of outliers and malicious clients	More computationally intensive
		Can improve model accuracy	
Secure Aggregation	Use techniques such as homomorphic encryption or secure multi-party computation to ensure privacy	Provides a high level of privacy protection	May be computationally expensive and slower than other aggregation methods
		Can still achieve good model accuracy	Requires careful implementation and management of security protocols
Differential Privacy Average Aggregation	Add random noise to the model updates before aggregation to ensure privacy	Provides a high level of privacy protection	May be slower and less efficient than other aggregation methods
			The level of noise added can impact model accuracy

¹⁴ Qi, P., Chiaro, D., Guzzo, A., Ianni, M., Fortino, G., & Piccialli, F. (2024). Model aggregation techniques in federated learning: A comprehensive survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 150, 272–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURE.2023.09.008>

Approach	Main Concept	Advantages	Disadvantages
Momentum Aggregation	Add a momentum term to the model updates before aggregation to improve convergence speed	Can improve convergence speed and reduce the impact of noisy or slow clients	May be sensitive to the choice of momentum term and the level of noise in the updates
Weighted Aggregation	Weight the contributions of different clients based on performance or other factors	Can improve model accuracy by giving more weight to more reliable or representative clients	Requires careful calibration of weights and may be sensitive to bias or noise in performance metrics
Bayesian Aggregation	Use Bayesian inference to aggregate model updates and take uncertainty into account	Can improve model generalization and reduce overfitting	Can be computationally expensive and require large amounts of data The Bayesian model assumptions may not hold for all types of data
Adversarial Aggregation	Detect and mitigate the impact of malicious clients or outlier model updates	Can improve model accuracy and reduce the impact of malicious clients	May be computationally expensive and require sophisticated detection and mitigation techniques
Quantization	Reduce the bit representation of model updates before transmission	Can improve communication efficiency and reduce bandwidth requirements	May introduce quantization error that can impact model accuracy The level of quantization needs to be carefully chosen
Hierarchical Aggregation	Perform aggregation at different levels of a hierarchical structure	Can improve communication efficiency by performing local aggregation at lower levels	Requires a well-defined hierarchical structure and careful management of data and aggregation protocols
Personalized Aggregation	Takes clients' unique characteristics into account	Improves model performance by adapting to individual client data	Maintains privacy, but may require additional communication and computational overhead
Ensemble-based Aggregation	Aggregate the model updates of multiple models trained on different subsets of the data	Can improve model accuracy by leveraging the diversity of the models	May be computationally expensive and require careful management of the ensemble models

3. Implementation of FL aggregation algorithms¹⁵

This section provides a summary implementations of the various algorithms discussed above, highlighting their respective features, such as aggregation approaches, improvements in convergence, security enhancements, communication efficiency, fault tolerance, security, client heterogeneity, and overall insights into advantages and disadvantages. This section is based on two prior systematic reviews that evaluated FL aggregation implementations^{15,16}. References for each implementation, including their specific methods and applications, can be found in **Appendix A**.

¹⁵ Qi, P., Chiaro, D., Guzzo, A., Ianni, M., Fortino, G., & Piccialli, F. (2024). Model aggregation techniques in federated learning: A comprehensive survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 150, 272–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURE.2023.09.008>

¹⁶ Guendouzi, B. S., Ouchani, S., el Assaad, H., & el Zaher, M. (2023). A systematic review of federated learning: Challenges, aggregation methods, and development tools. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 220, 103714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JNCA.2023.103714>

Year	Name	Model Aggregation	Aggregation approach	Convergence Reduction	Heterogeneity	Security	Communication Cost	Computation Cost	Fault Tolerance	Learning Quality	Scalability	Personalization
2017	FedAvg	✓	Averaging Aggregation									
2019	RFA	✓	Averaging Aggregation			✓						
2020	SCAFFOLD	✓	Secure Aggregation	✓			✓					
2020	FedOPT	✓	Weighted Aggregation	✓	✓							
2020	FedADAGAR		Differential Privacy Average Aggregation									
2020	FedBoost		Ensemble-Based Aggregation				✓					
2020	FedProx		Weighted Aggregation	✓	✓							
2020	FedMA	✓	Personalized Aggregation				✓					
2020	LAQ		Quantization Aggregation				✓					
2020	SAFA	✓	Secure Aggregation				✓	✓	✓			
2021	FedDist		Weighted Aggregation		✓							✓
2021	FEDHQ	✓	Quantization Aggregation	✓								
2021	FAIR	✓	Personalized Aggregation							✓		
2021	FedPSO		Ensemble-Based Aggregation				✓			✓		
2021	LEGATO		Personalized Aggregation			✓	✓	✓			✓	
2021	MHAT	✓	Personalized Aggregation		✓			✓				
2021	SEAR		Secure Aggregation			✓		✓				
2021	Turbo-Aggregate	✓	Secure Aggregation					✓			✓	
2022	EPPDA		Secure Aggregation			✓			✓			
2022	FedBuff	✓	Ensemble-Based Aggregation									
2022	HeteroSAg	✓	Secure Aggregation			✓	✓					
2022	LightSecAgg		Secure Aggregation					✓	✓			

3.1. FedAvg

- **Features:** Utilizes Federated Stochastic Gradient Descent (FedSGD), where each client performs one local epoch of training, and gradients are averaged to update the global model. The key feature is simplicity and ease of implementation.
- **Advantages:** Simple iterative model averaging, making it suitable for a variety of applications. Easy to implement in practice.
- **Disadvantages:** Struggles with convergence, particularly in non-IID data settings, and is slower when the data distribution is not uniform across clients.

3.2. RFA (Robust Federated Aggregation)

- **Features:** Uses geometric median to aggregate model updates, providing robustness against malicious updates (e.g., poisoning attacks). Ensures that individual client data is never exposed during aggregation.
- **Advantages:** Provides robust performance in the presence of adversarial updates.
- **Disadvantages:** Computationally complex, and the geometric median can slow down aggregation compared to simple averaging methods such as FedAvg.

3.3. SCAFFOLD

- **Features:** Corrects for client drift using a control variate approach, which mitigates the variance introduced by local updates in non-IID settings.
- **Advantages:** Accelerates convergence and is more robust to heterogeneous data.
- **Disadvantages:** More computationally intensive, and implementing control variates can be difficult in large-scale systems.

3.4. FedOPT

- **Features:** FedOPT is a generalization of FedAvg where the server optimizes the aggregation using a server-side optimizer rather than simply averaging the updates from clients. This allows for more flexible and adaptive global model updates.
- **Advantages:** Accelerates convergence by using adaptive optimizers, particularly useful for non-IID data environments. Provides flexibility in optimizing global model updates based on client data distribution.

- **Disadvantages:** May require careful tuning of the server-side optimizer to avoid overfitting or underfitting during aggregation, increasing implementation complexity.

3.5. FedADAGAR

- **Features:** FedADAGAR stands for Federated Adaptive Gradient Aggregation with Regularization. This algorithm enhances convergence in federated learning by incorporating adaptive gradient methods while regularizing client model updates to address data heterogeneity and system variability.
- **Advantages:** It improves the convergence rate, particularly in heterogeneous data environments, by adapting gradient steps and reducing the variance across clients' updates.
- **Disadvantages:** The algorithm's complexity increases due to the adaptive gradient adjustments and regularization, which also may require more computation and fine-tuning.

3.6. FedBoost

- **Features:** Uses ensemble learning by aggregating pre-trained base models, reducing the burden of full model training on each client. Focuses on memory and communication efficiency.
- **Advantages:** Reduces communication costs, particularly beneficial for clients with limited computational resources.
- **Disadvantages:** Model performance depends on the quality and configuration of the base models, requiring careful tuning.

3.7. FedProx

- **Features:** Extends FedAvg by introducing a proximal term in the objective function to handle heterogeneity in both data and devices. This prevents large divergence between local and global models.
- **Advantages:** More robust to heterogeneity and improves convergence in non-IID data environments.
- **Disadvantages:** Convergence may still be slower than simpler methods due to the added regularization term.

3.8. FedMA

- **Features:** Aggregates models layer-by-layer rather than full model updates. Particularly suited for convolutional and recurrent neural networks (CNNs and LSTMs). Matching of neurons in the first layer drives model synchronization.
- **Advantages:** Reduces communication load by sharing one layer at a time and matches neurons to improve feature extraction.
- **Disadvantages:** Increased computational complexity due to layer-wise matching.

3.9. LAQ

- **Features:** Skips unimportant gradient updates and quantizes gradients to reduce the amount of data exchanged between clients and the server.
- **Advantages:** Minimizes communication overhead and increases efficiency.
- **Disadvantages:** Skipping updates may lead to suboptimal model performance if important updates are omitted.

3.10. SAFA (Semi-Synchronous FL)

- **Features:** Combines synchronous and asynchronous aggregation to handle client-server stragglers and stale models, improving global model convergence.
- **Advantages:** Balances the need for synchronization while reducing delays caused by slow clients (stragglers).
- **Disadvantages:** More complex to manage, particularly with respect to coordination between synchronous and asynchronous updates.

3.11. FedDist

- **Features:** Customizes model layers based on the client's specific characteristics and the dissimilarities between neurons in different client models.
- **Advantages:** Allows for better personalization, improving performance on heterogeneous and non-IID data.
- **Disadvantages:** Significantly increases communication costs by adjusting neuron counts in each layer for every client.

3.12. FedHQ

- **Features:** Introduces a heterogeneous quantization method that dynamically corrects quantization errors during aggregation to improve convergence speed.
- **Advantages:** Fast convergence with reduced communication overhead due to quantization error correction.
- **Disadvantages:** Increased computational load at the server for handling dynamic error corrections.

3.13. FAIR

- **Features:** Introduces a quality-aware incentive mechanism to prioritize high-quality client updates for aggregation. Only the best-performing models are aggregated.
- **Advantages:** Improves the overall quality of the global model by focusing on the best local models.
- **Disadvantages:** Risk of excluding valuable updates from clients that may not meet high-quality thresholds, leading to potential biases.

3.14. FedPSO

- **Features:** Uses Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to optimize client contributions based on network conditions, allowing for better performance in resource-constrained environments.
- **Advantages:** Robust against unstable networks, reduces data transmission overhead.
- **Disadvantages:** Performs less effectively in high-quality, stable networks compared to other methods.

3.15. LEGATO

- **Features:** Implements layer-specific gradient aggregation, which allows for fine-grained control over each layer's updates, enhancing robustness against Byzantine attacks.
- **Advantages:** Improves computational efficiency by processing gradients at the layer level.

- **Disadvantages:** Requires careful tuning of layer-specific parameters, adding complexity to the aggregation process.

3.16. MHAT

- **Features:** Uses knowledge distillation to aggregate heterogeneous model outputs, allowing clients to use different model architectures.
- **Advantages:** Reduces computational burden on clients and supports heterogeneous models.
- **Disadvantages:** Sophisticated server-side aggregation is required to combine different model architectures.

3.17. SEAR

- **Features:** Relies on Intel SGX to protect client models from Byzantine attacks while efficiently managing memory for secure aggregation.
- **Advantages:** Robust against Byzantine attacks with efficient memory management.
- **Disadvantages:** Memory limitations in Intel SGX could slow down processing, especially with large models.

3.18. Turbo-Aggregate

- **Features:** Uses a circular multi-group strategy to speed up aggregation and improve scalability in large-scale FL systems.
- **Advantages:** Increases aggregation speed by up to 40x and scales well to large numbers of users.
- **Disadvantages:** Requires optimized secret-sharing protocols to handle increased user numbers efficiently

3.19. EPPDA

- **Features:** Incorporates fault-tolerant privacy-preserving methods using secret-sharing, making it robust to disconnections and reverse attacks.
- **Advantages:** Strong privacy guarantees and robustness against disruptions.
- **Disadvantages:** Requires high computational resources to manage the secret-sharing process.

3.20. FedBuff

- **Features:** Balances synchronous and asynchronous FL updates by using a buffer system to improve convergence and reduce communication delays.
- **Advantages:** Combines the best features of synchronous and asynchronous FL for more efficient training.
- **Disadvantages:** The complexity of implementing buffer management adds to the system's overhead.

3.21. HeteroSAg (2022)

- **Features:** Adapts to heterogeneous client resources by dividing local model updates into segments and coordinating updates based on resource availability.
- **Advantages:** Provides flexibility for clients with varying resources and improves robustness against Byzantine attacks.
- **Disadvantages:** Requires complex coordination to manage segmented updates, increasing overall system complexity.

3.22. LightSecAgg (2022)

- **Features:** Uses mask-coding and decoding to handle client dropouts, reducing the overhead associated with aggregating masked updates.
- **Advantages:** Improves resilience to dropout and speeds up data exchange by reducing overhead.
- **Disadvantages:** Performance improvements may be limited when dealing with large-scale datasets.

4. Overview of open source FL frameworks

The field of FL has seen the development of a variety of open-source tools and frameworks, each integrating a diverse range of FL algorithms discussed above. This section highlights some of the most popular open-source frameworks as well as frameworks that support the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM), which can be potentially meet the specific needs of PHEMS clinical use cases.

Framework	Language	ML libraries	HFL	VFL	FTL	Scalability	Security	Main aggregation method
Fate	Python	PyTorch, TensorFlow	✓	✓		✓	SMPC, DP	FedAvg
Substra	Python	PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Scikit-learn	✓			✓	SMPC	FedAvg
Pysyft	Python	PyTorch	✓	✓	✓		SMPC, HE	FedAvg
PyGrid	Python	PyTorch TensorFlow	✓	✓	✓	✓	SMPC, DP	FedAvg
Flower	Python	PyTorch TensorFlow Keras	✓			✓	SMPC	Multiple
TensorFlow Federated (TFF)	Python	Tensorflow	✓	✓	✓	✓	DP	FedAvg and FedSGD
FedML	Python	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		Multiple

4.1. FATE (Federated AI Technology Enabler Framework)¹⁷

FATE (Federated AI Technology Enabler) is an industrial-grade federated learning platform developed by Webank's AI Department. It supports horizontal federated learning, vertical federated learning, and federated transfer learning. For model aggregation, FATE uses methods such as FedAvg for HFL, SecureBoost for VFL, and FTL for heterogeneous data scenarios. FATE includes various privacy-preserving techniques, and supports algorithms such as linear regression, logistic regression, deep learning models, and XGBoost. It operates in Python and offers deployment scalability with tools as KubeFATE for Kubernetes integration.

4.2. Substra¹⁸

Substra supports Python programming and is compatible with machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Scikit-learn. Substra uses federated averaging as the primary model aggregation method, with a centralized structure where weight updates are averaged and shared across nodes. It also implements secure multi-party computation to ensure data privacy.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/FederatedAI/FATE>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/substra>

4.3. PySyft¹⁹

PySyft is built on PyTorch and enables secure computations with data encryption techniques such as homomorphic encryption (HE) and SMPC. PySyft's primary aggregation method is FedAvg.

4.4. PyGrid²⁰

PyGrid is a peer-to-peer platform that leverages the PySyft framework. PyGrid uses FedAvg as the core aggregation method, and incorporates SMPC and differential privacy for secure computations on distributed data. PyGrid supports ML models from frameworks such as PyTorch and TensorFlow..

4.5. FLOWER²¹

Flower is a flexible open-source framework that supports machine learning libraries such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Keras, making it versatile for a variety of ML models, including deep learning and traditional algorithms. The primary aggregation method used in Flower is FedAvg, but also supports other methods such as FedProx and FedOPT.

4.6. TensorFlow Federated (TFF)²²

TFF is built with Python and leverages the TensorFlow library for model training and deployment. TFF supports HFL but is flexible for integration with vertical federated learning and federated transfer learning use cases. For security, differential privacy is integrated. TFF primarily uses FedAvg algorithm as its main aggregation method.

4.7. FedML²³

FedML supports horizontal, vertical and federated transfer learning. Developed with flexibility, it offers tools for performance measurement, result analysis, and uses differential

¹⁹ <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft>

²⁰ <https://github.com/OpenMined/PyGrid-deprecated---see-PySyft->

²¹ <https://github.com/adap/flower>

²² <https://github.com/google-parfait/tensorflow-federated>

²³ <https://github.com/FedML-AI/FedML>

privacy and SMPC for security. FedML incorporates several aggregation algorithms, including.

4.1. FL implementations using OMOP CDM

FL frameworks that support OMOP compatibility are crucial for PHEMS, as the clinical data in this project is mapped using the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM). OMOP provides a standardized way to represent healthcare data, making it essential for institutions involved in PHEMS to collaborate effectively without sharing sensitive raw data. The integration of OMOP-compatible FL frameworks ensures that machine learning models can be trained on standardized, structured data while ensuring privacy and interoperability across different hospitals.

4.1.1. VANTAGE6²⁴

VANTAGE6 (priVAcY preserviNg federaTed leArninG infrastruCTurE for Secure Insight eXchange) is an open-source, privacy-preserving federated learning FL framework designed for decentralized data analysis, making it particularly suited for healthcare applications. By allowing institutions to collaborate on machine learning projects without needing to centralize sensitive patient data, VANTAGE6 aligns with the goals of the PHEMS, where data is mapped according to the OMOP CDM.

Key Features:

- **Privacy-preserving design:** VANTAGE6 ensures that patient data remains within the local environment of each institution, transmitting only aggregated results to the central server. This setup addresses concerns around data privacy and regulatory compliance (e.g., GDPR).
- **Support for horizontally and vertically partitioned data:** The framework is versatile, supporting both horizontally partitioned data (where institutions have different patients with the same data features) and vertically partitioned data (where institutions have the same patients but different data features). This flexibility allows

²⁴ Moncada-Torres, A., Martin, F., Sieswerda, M., Soest, J. van, & Geleijnse, G. (n.d.). VANTAGE6: an open source priVAcY preserviNg federaTed leArninG infrastruCTurE for Secure Insight eXchange. <https://distributedlearning.ai/>
<https://github.com/vantage6/vantage6>

VANTAGE6 to handle various clinical datasets across multiple institutions, which is essential for PHEMS.

- **Modular architecture:** VANTAGE6 uses a client-server model where the researcher sends computation requests to a central server, which are then processed at the local nodes. The nodes execute the algorithm using Docker containers, ensuring that any algorithm, regardless of the programming language, can be deployed. This supports easy integration with OMOP CDM-mapped data and other healthcare data structures.
- **Autonomy and flexibility:** Each institution retains control over its data and can decide how much of it is shared for model training. This autonomy ensures that institutions can participate in federated learning without compromising on data governance policies or security.

Application in Healthcare:

VANTAGE6 has been successfully used in several healthcare research projects. For example, it facilitated a federated Cox proportional hazards model across Dutch and Taiwanese cancer registries, allowing the comparison of patient outcomes without sharing individual-level data^{25,26}. This demonstrates the framework's ability to manage cross-institutional collaborations, where patient privacy is critical, making it an ideal solution for projects such as PHEMS that rely on OMOP-standardized datasets.

OMOP Integration:

Though not originally designed for OMOP, VANTAGE6's flexible, container-based architecture allows it to be extended for use with OMOP CDM data. By leveraging Docker containers and a standardized API, it can seamlessly process OMOP-structured data for federated learning, providing a scalable solution for multi-institutional collaborations in the PHEMS project.

4.2. Evaluation criteria to choose FL frameworks

To determine which federated learning frameworks are best suited for implementation within the PHEMS infrastructure (Section 5.1) and the clinical use cases, it is crucial to establish a

²⁵ Yong Li, Xiaoqian Jiang, Shuang Wang, Hongkai Xiong, and Lucila Ohno-Machado. VERTical Grid lOGistic regression (VERTIGO). *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 23(3):570–579, 20

²⁶ Arturo Moncada-Torres, Frank Martin, Katja Aben, et al. The effect of synoptic reporting on prostate cancer survivability: Centralized and federated analysis. Under review, 2020.

structured evaluation protocol. This protocol will assess frameworks across four key dimensions: Security, Features, Interoperability, and User Friendliness, ensuring alignment with the project's technical requirements, deployment environment, and ease of use. In particular, PHEMS we will prioritize frameworks that are OMOP-compatible and allow for flexibility in customization, such as modifying merging and aggregation algorithms and integrating various machine learning libraries. Moreover, these frameworks must support interoperability and be compatible with containerization platforms like Docker and Kubernetes, ensuring smooth deployment.

4.2.1. Security mechanisms

Security mechanisms are fundamental to Federated Learning frameworks as they ensure the privacy and protection of sensitive data during the training process:

- **Differential privacy:** A technique that adds noise to data or model updates to prevent the disclosure of individual data points.
- **Homomorphic encryption:** Allows computations to be performed on encrypted data without decrypting it, ensuring data privacy is maintained throughout the processing. The presence of built-in support for homomorphic encryption is a key consideration.
- **Secure multiparty computation:** Ensures that multiple parties can jointly compute a function over their inputs while keeping those inputs private. A framework's ability to natively support SMC is a significant advantage.

4.2.2. Features

FL model aggregation algorithms

It is important that the chosen FL frameworks support the use of diverse aggregation algorithms and allow for customization to effectively address the different use cases. This includes standard aggregation algorithms such as FedAvg or FedSGD but also the ability to customize the merging process. Key considerations include whether the framework supports weighted or non-weighted merging and allows for the use of alternative merging functions, beyond simple averaging. Customization capabilities that enable users to implement or modify aggregation methods to meet the specific needs of different use cases are essential for optimal performance and flexibility.

Compatibility with ML libraries

Compatibility with machine learning libraries is a fundamental aspect of any FL framework, as it enables the building and training of various machine learning models. This includes the availability of built-in, federated-compatible models that can be readily deployed for common tasks like classification, regression, and clustering. Additionally, support for popular machine learning libraries such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Keras is crucial, as it allows developers to use familiar tools and leverage existing codebases for model development. This compatibility is particularly important for use cases such as the prediction of sepsis and hemophilia, where there is a need to develop or scale up existing algorithms effectively.

Compatibility with different FL paradigms

FL frameworks should support paradigms that handle different types of data distributions: e.g., horizontal federated learning where datasets across different clients share the same feature space but differ in samples or vertical federated learning where datasets share the same samples but differ in feature space. Both paradigms are relevant within PHEMS given that data controllers have diverse samples sizes and features in their database.

4.2.3. Interoperability

Interoperability is a critical aspect of evaluating FL frameworks, as it determines the ease with which a framework can be integrated into the PHEMS architecture. This includes the availability of pre-built deployment packages or scripts or features such as model compression and quantization, which reduce model size and computational requirements to ensure efficient execution

GPU Support

GPU support is critical for accelerating model training, especially when the project is scale up and the sample size or complexity of the models increases.

Docker and Kubernetes

The ability to effectively manage and deploy containerized environments is a fundamental aspect of any FL framework. Docker containerization provides a standardized environment for deploying and running FL frameworks, ensuring compatibility. Docker enables applications to be packaged and run in containers—loosely isolated environments that

encapsulate all necessary libraries, settings, and tools. This isolation ensures security and allows multiple containers to run simultaneously on a host, providing a robust solution for bundling software and its dependencies into a transportable unit that can operate seamlessly across diverse computing environments. Additionally, Kubernetes, a portable and extensible open-source platform, manages these containerized workloads and services, facilitating declarative configuration and automation. These tools are central to the PHEMS infrastructure, as described in [Deliverable D2.1](#).

4.2.4. User friendliness

User friendliness is a crucial aspect of evaluating federated learning (FL) frameworks, as it directly impacts the ease of use and overall user experience, particularly for developers who may not have extensive experience with FL. These frameworks should include comprehensive documentation and additional support materials such as forums and tutorials. Ideally, these frameworks should provide tools to assess the performance of models trained using the framework, support for custom metrics, and the overall integration of these tools into the training workflow.

4.3. Recent systematic reviews comparing FL frameworks

A recent study systematically assessed the performance of 15 open-source FL frameworks (Figure 4)²⁷. Each criterion within the categories of features, interoperability, and user friendliness was assigned a specific weight based on its relevance, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of each framework's overall capability and suitability for different use cases. Flower, FLARE, and FederatedScope are recommended for users seeking robust feature sets and high interoperability. EasyFL is ideal for developers who prioritize ease of use and quick setup. Regarding **VANTAGE6**, even though this framework is not included in this comparative analysis, it should still be strongly considered for PHEMS due to its proven compatibility with OMOP and demonstrated applications in healthcare studies.

²⁷ Riedel, P., Schick, L., von Schwerin, R., Reichert, M., Schaudt, D., & Hafner, A. (2024). Comparative analysis of open-source federated learning frameworks - a literature-based survey and review. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-024-02234-z>.

Figure 4: Results of a comparative from a comparative analysis of open-source federated learning frameworks. The tools are ranked with scores between 0-100%, based on the criteria described in Section 4.2.

5. Implementation of FL tools in PHEMS architecture

5.1. Summary of PHEMS system architecture

This section provides a brief overview of the PHEMS federation architecture, highlighting key components relevant to implementing federated learning tools. The architecture is built to facilitate collaborative research and analytics while adhering to stringent data protection regulations. It comprises several key components, each serving a distinct function to ensure the seamless operation of federated learning and data sharing across the network. For a comprehensive understanding and further details on the architecture, readers are encouraged to [Deliverable D2.1](#). The PHEMS architecture is designed to enable deployment of various open-source frameworks discussed above. Its robust infrastructure that includes secure computing environments, support for containerization (e.g., Docker and Kubernetes), will allow for seamless integration.

5.1.1. Federated learning orchestrator:

This central component is pivotal in managing the federated learning process. It acts as the primary coordinator, distributing machine learning model training tasks and parameters to each participating hospital's data silo. The orchestrator aggregates the model updates—such as gradients or weights—computed locally by each data silo, combining them into a global model. This global model is then redistributed to all participants, allowing iterative improvement without the need for raw data exchange. This approach ensures that data privacy is maintained, as only model parameters are shared, not the underlying data itself

5.1.2. Data Controllers and Federated Nodes

Each participating hospital operates as a data controller, responsible for managing its local datasets and ensuring compliance with privacy regulations. Within the technical architecture, each hospital hosts a federated node, which is a secure computation environment built using Kubernetes. These federated nodes facilitate local training of machine learning models using the hospital's data. The nodes are designed to handle computations in a secure and isolated manner. This setup also supports the execution of visiting algorithms, which can interact with local datasets to perform specific analytical tasks without data being moved outside the hospital's secure perimeter.

5.1.3. Processing Layer

The processing layer, among other functions, will support federated learning, enabling the execution of data analysis tasks across distributed datasets while keeping the data localized.

5.1.4. MLOps Architecture:

The PHEMS project integrates MLOps (Machine Learning Operations) principles to manage the lifecycle of machine learning models deployed across the network. This includes centralized DevOps services and CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment) pipelines that automate the testing, validation, deployment, and monitoring of machine learning models. The MLOps architecture utilizes Kubernetes clusters to provide scalable and secure deployment environments for FL models, ensuring that models are consistently updated, monitored, and optimized across all federated nodes. This infrastructure supports rapid development and deployment cycles, enhancing the overall efficiency and reliability of the federated learning process

5.1.5. Security and privacy measure

The architecture incorporates comprehensive security and privacy measures to protect sensitive health data and ensure compliance with regulations like GDPR. These measures include secure network communications, stringent access controls, and data encryption at rest and in transit. Continuous monitoring and auditing mechanisms are in place to detect and respond to any security breaches or anomalies, ensuring that all data processing activities are transparent and accountable. The architecture also supports the use of trusted execution environments and differential privacy techniques to enhance data security and privacy further.

5.2. PHEMS hackathon - UC2: Development of ML models to predict sepsis in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU)

In collaboration with Work Packages 4 and 6, we will organize a hackathon in January 2025, with the aim of engaging developers in a competition to build ML models that can detect sepsis early. Although the focus of this initial phase is on centralized ML, the ultimate goal is to identify the best algorithms, which will later be adapted for implementation within a federated learning framework. This two-step approach will help us understand the requirements and challenges related to developing effective prediction algorithms that can be implemented with OMOP-compatible frameworks for a real use case within PHEMS, once the federate architecture is in place.

5.2.1. Definition of the Challenge

The objective of this challenge is to develop an algorithm for the early detection of sepsis. To facilitate this, participants will receive patient data from a retrospective registry that includes key variables relevant to sepsis prediction. These variables are mapped according to the OMOP CDM and span demographics, vital signs, laboratory results and physical examinations. Participants will also be provided with multiple sepsis definitions based on predefined criteria^{28, 29}.

²⁸ <https://www.icd10data.com/>

²⁹ <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2814296>

Participants must:

- Conduct exploratory data analysis to determine which variables are most meaningful for prediction.
- Build a ML-based prediction algorithm to predict the onset of sepsis.
- Compete to achieve the highest utility score, a custom function that rewards early detection while penalizing late or false predictions.

The utility function emphasizes predictions that occur within the critical time window of 8-12 hours before and up to 3 hours after sepsis diagnosis. Predictions outside of this window will be penalized, as will false positive or negative predictions.

5.2.2. Dataset

The dataset used in this challenge provided by *Hospital Sant Joan de Déu (Barcelona)* and includes de-identified patient records from PICU patients. The dataset is divided into three subsets:

- **Training Set:** Available for participants to build their models.
- **Testing Set:** Used for internal validation.
- **Private Set:** Reserved for scoring and determining the best performing algorithms.

This dataset provides an extensive range of features relevant for the prediction of sepsis, such as time-series vital signs and laboratory results, structured according to the OMOP CDM. By ensuring consistency in data structure, we facilitate the transition from centralized to federated learning, a key aspect of the future steps in the PHEMS project.

5.2.3. Evaluation and Scoring

Algorithms will be evaluated on the following metrics:

- **Time-to-Positive:** Rewarding predictions that fall within the predefined time window (8-12 hours before and up to 3 hours after diagnosis).
- **AUC-ROC:** Measuring the ability of the model to distinguish between sepsis and non-sepsis cases.
- **Precision and Recall:** Focusing on the accuracy and completeness of the predictions.

The custom **utility function** calculates the overall score, rewarding early detection while penalizing missed sepsis cases or false positives. The winning team will be the one whose algorithm achieves the highest utility score on the private dataset.

5.2.4. Post-Hackathon federated learning implementation

The primary goal of the hackathon is to develop robust, high-performing algorithms in a centralized learning environment. However, this is only the first step in a broader strategy. Once the top-performing models are identified, we will evaluate their potential for implementation within a federated learning framework, aligned with the PHEMS architecture. As part of this evaluation process, several key considerations will be addressed:

1. **Suitability for federated learning:** We will assess the performance and structure of the best algorithms to determine if they can be efficiently adapted to a federated learning environment. Specific focus will be placed on understanding how well the models can operate when trained across decentralized datasets that remain local at each institution.
2. **Model Aggregation:** A critical aspect is choosing the appropriate model aggregation method. Algorithms outlined in Section 3 will be explored, based on the specific requirements of the centralized algorithms.
3. **Security mechanisms:** Federated learning introduces additional privacy and security considerations, particularly around ensuring that model updates (gradients or weights) do not expose sensitive patient data. To safeguard privacy, we will evaluate security mechanisms such as differential privacy, secure multi-party computation and homomorphic encryption
4. **OMOP CDM compatibility:** We will ensure that the top-performing models can be seamlessly integrated with OMOP-compatible FL frameworks.

By conducting this thorough evaluation of the best algorithms from the hackathon, we will gain insights into the practical challenges of adapting centralized models to PHEMS federated architecture.

6. Appendix A

Table 3: References for FL aggregation methods outlined in Section 2.

Year	Name	Reference
2017	FedAVG	https://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/mcmahan17a?ref=https://githubhelp.com
2019	RFA	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9721118
2020	SCAFFOLD	https://proceedings.mlr.press/v119/karimireddy20a.html
2020	FedOPT	https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.00295
2020	FedADAGAR	https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.00295
2020	FedYOGI	https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.00295
2020	FedBoost	https://proceedings.mlr.press/v119/hamer20a.html
2020	FedProx	https://proceedings.mlsys.org/paper_files/paper/2020/hash/1f5fe83998a09396ebe6477d9475ba0c-Abstract.html
2020	FedMA	https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.06440
2020	LAQ	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9238427
2020	SAFA	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9093123
2021	FedDist	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9488743
2021	FEDHQ	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9425020
2021	FAIR	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9488743
2021	FedPSO	https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/2/600
2021	LEGATO	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9582211
2021	MHAT	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0020025521000840?via%3Dihub
2021	SEAR	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0020025521000840?via%3Dihub
2021	Turbo-Aggregate	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9336021
2022	EPPDA	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1335465
2022	FedBuff	https://proceedings.mlr.press/v151/nguyen22b.html
2022	HeteroSAg	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9712310
2022	LightSecAgg	https://proceedings.mlsys.org/paper_files/paper/2022/hash/6c44dc73014d66ba49b28d483a8f8b0d-Abstract.html